

TRANSLATION PROBLEMS OF TOURISM TERMINOLOGY FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7191428>

Abstract. Currently, a lot of work is being done on the development of the country's economy. In particular, we are witnessing rapid changes in the field of tourism, which is one of the main links of economic development. It would not be an exaggeration to say that the decisions and decrees issued by our president in the field of tourism today are great steps taken to fill the gaps in this regard and bring tourism to the national level. This article discusses the problems of translating tourism terminology from English to Uzbek.

Keywords: tourism terminology, development of the country's economy, globalization, beautiful recreation areas, tourist destinations.

ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПЕРЕВОДА ТУРИСТИЧЕСКОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ С АНГЛИЙСКОГО НА УЗБЕКСКИЙ ЯЗЫК

Аннотация. В настоящее время проводится большая работа по развитию экономики страны. В частности, мы наблюдаем стремительные изменения в сфере туризма, который является одним из основных звеньев экономического развития. Не будет преувеличением сказать, что решения и указы, изданные нашим президентом в сфере туризма сегодня, являются большими шагами, предпринятыми для восполнения пробелов в этом отношении и вывода туризма на национальный уровень. В данной статье рассматриваются проблемы перевода туристической терминологии с английского языка на узбекский.

Ключевые слова: терминология туризма, развитие экономики страны, глобализация, красивые зоны отдыха, туристические дестинации.

INTRODUCTION

Globalization and integration of the processes taking place in the field of tourism in the world has motivated to raise the quality of the tourism sector of our country to a new level. Uzbekistan is one of the countries with great potential in the field of tourism. Today, it is necessary to take advantage of the unique nature of our country, beautiful recreation areas, to develop new tourist destinations, pilgrimage tourism, ecological, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic tourism and other branches of this field, and to pay special attention to the issue of personnel. The tourism sector is one of the most promising sectors that bring high income to the national economy. "One of our priority tasks in the economic sphere is to further strengthen the economic relations of our country with foreign countries and to increase its international prestige by widely promoting the economic opportunities of our republic abroad, to accelerate the attraction of investments, and to further develop the tourism sector."

This, in turn, brought about the need for the development of the tourism sector, the need for a more detailed study of the system of terms related to the tourism sector, which is actively used in this sector, from both a scientific and a practical point of view. Today, the tourism terminology in our country is at the stage of development, and in this process, the English language tourism terminology, which is a globally recognized tool of international communication, plays an important role. The development of the tourism industry is inextricably linked to translation and intercultural communication. A unique feature of tourism

is the integration of a number of industries: hotel industry, restaurant business, credit and financial organizations, and entertainment industries are among them. "Tourism is not only the study of regions, but also a cultural system that reflects the process of its creation and change." The tourism sector is the third most profitable sector of the world economy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Today, the system of touristic terminology creates the direction of systems linguistics related to the field of tourism. The penetration of these concepts into all fields requires the creation of explanatory and translation dictionaries for the needs of mankind. In such dictionaries, word formation through translation and the specific linguistic features of terminological units related to the field of tourism in different systematic languages are reflected through comparative translation. The change of terms from year to year and the emergence of new terms are inextricably linked with the development of the fields of science, education, production and innovation. Naturally, due to the development of fields, due to the wide use of the achievements of various experts in this field, attention to terms increases and new terms appear.

Various problems arise in the process of translating scientific texts containing terms related to various fields in other foreign languages into Uzbek or vice versa. Today, one of the first problems is that it is impossible to find a term that corresponds to the meaning of the term in this text, when translating from another language. This is a big challenge. Before that, it is possible to touch on a small issue, there are no manuals on field terms created in Uzbek for translating terms from other languages (English) into Uzbek, even if they are incomplete, which is a big problem for translators and language learners in translating terms. causes problems. In our opinion, this third problem arises through the above issues, this problem is that after the term being translated from another language does not match this word in our native language, another foreign word is accepted as it is (kalka), and if we see the translation of that word in the native language, it gives the wrong meaning.

RESULTS

Today, it can be considered an important problem in the field of translation of terms. The entry and assimilation of words from one language to another is not just a simple process, but a regularity associated with complex linguistic and socio-historical conditions. First of all, real conditions are necessary for the acquisition of words from one language to another. Such conditions are mutual cooperation of languages, that is, communication between languages.

As a result of the incompatibility of the tourism sector system, it is possible to include non-alternative terms, i.e., realities that do not exist in the tourism sector discourse of another country, into the unit of the non-alternative term. Explanatory translation is used when a word or phrase in the original does not have a variant or equivalent in the lexicon of the language being translated, and its explanation, that is, an image of the concept expressed by this unit, is used in the translation process. Interest in the translation of tourism terminology into different languages serves the continuous improvement of terms related to the field of tourism. The change of terms from year to year and the emergence of new terms are inextricably linked with the development of the fields of science, education, production and innovation. The urgency of studying the problems of translation of terms related to the field of tourism is mainly related to the development of international relations, the expansion of cooperation between local and foreign companies, as well as the training of professional personnel in this field.

DISCUSSION

The development of the tourism industry has a positive effect on the improvement of internal economic structures, as well as on the development of industries related to this industry. But it is no secret that large financial resources are required to travel, to rest in a place other than the place of permanent residence, to see new areas or to restore health in healing areas. These funds are spent on getting to the desired destination, overnight stay and accommodation, meals and the use of various services. It is expedient to partially use the state's social protection policy for the segments of the population in need of social protection. In developed countries, systems of organizing special trips for these population groups have been introduced, and through them it is ensured that tourism services serve precisely the poor segments of the population.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we can say that creating explanatory, electronic and translation dictionaries of existing tourism terms in the Uzbek language is one of the important tasks of Uzbek terminology. Giving and explaining terms in explanatory dictionaries and special dictionaries for touristic terms serves to familiarize the student with the most necessary and general concepts of this subject and to increase his level of knowledge, as well as to create interest in this field.

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